

Title: SQL On Hadoop – Architecture, Technology and Innovations

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INTRODUCTION: This presentation gives an exhaustive overview of the architectural and technological underpinnings of SQL on Hadoop solutions of today. It covers architectures of low latency SQL engines on Hadoop for structured, unstructured and streaming analytics as well as SQL for Operational Systems and Operational Analytics on Hadoop. The talk also covers the innovations happening in the space with probabilistic engines like BlinkDB to GPU based engines like MapD.

ABSTRACT

With the rapid adoption of Hadoop in the enterprise it has become all the more important to build SQL Engines on Hadoop for all kinds of workloads for almost all kind of end users and use cases. From low latency analytics based SQL to ACID based semantics on Hadoop for Operational Systems, to SQL for handling unstructured and streaming data, SQL is fast becoming the lingua-franca in the big data world too. The talk focuses on the exciting tools, technologies and innovations and their underlying architectures and the exciting road ahead in this space. This is a fiercely competitive landscape with vendors and innovators trying to capture mindshare and piece of the pie – with a whole suite of innovations like – index based SQL solutions in Hadoop to OLAP with Apache Kylin and Tajo to BlinkDB and MapD.

Topics :

- Why SQL on Hadoop
- Challenges of SQL on Hadoop
- SQL on Hadoop Architectures for Low Latency Analytics (Drill, Impala, Presto, SparkSQL, JethroData)
- SQL on Hadoop Architecture for Semi-Structured Data
- SQL on Hadoop Architecture for Streaming Data
- Innovations (OLAP on Hadoop, Probabilistic SQL Engines, GPU Based SQL Solutions)

KEYWORDS:

BIOGRAPHY:

Published Author with Apress - "SQL on Big Data - Technology, Architecture and Innovations", Sumit has more than 22 years of experience in the Software Industry in various roles spanning companies from startups to enterprises.

Sumit is an Independent Consultant working with big data, data visualisation and data science and a software architect building end-to-end data-driven analytic systems.

Sumit has worked for Microsoft (SQL server development team), Oracle (OLAP development team) and Verizon (Big Data analytics team) in a career spanning 22 years.

Currently, he works for multiple clients advising them on their data architectures and big data solutions and does hands on coding with Spark, Scala, Java and Python.

Sumit has MS and BS in Computer Science.

Sumit has hiked to Mt. Everest Base camp in Oct, 2016.